

FluenTFM: Development of a neutronics-thermohydraulics coupling code for molten salt reactors

Max Begue^{1,2,*}, Axel Laureau¹, Elsa Merle¹, Julien Vukasin²

¹Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, Grenoble INP, LPSC-IN2P3, 38000 Grenoble, France;

²Orano, 92320 Châtillon, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804040

ABSTRACT

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) have been considered an increasingly promising technology over the past two decades. Indeed, this type of reactor may provide safety and flexibility advantages that make for a promising design. For this study, the focus is set on designs where the fuel circulates and also serves as the coolant. This means that the coupling between neutronics and thermohydraulics is very strong, requiring dedicated codes for simulation. In this work, FluenTFM is introduced. This new code couples the computational fluid dynamics commercial solver Ansys Fluent with the Transient Fission Matrices (TFM) approach. This choice was made to benefit from all the validations and the robustness of the Fluent solver, while retaining a user-friendly interface. The TFM approach was chosen for neutronics due to its ability to solve quickly spatial kinetics with a precision similar to a Monte Carlo simulation during the coupling iterations.

Details about both sides of the coupling and its implementation are provided before comparing the results of reactivity insertion transients with TFM-OpenFOAM as reference code. The comparison is performed on a fast MSR derived from the Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR) design and both codes demonstrate good agreement in steady-state simulations and in reactivity insertion transients.

Keywords: Molten Salt Reactor, coupling, neutronics, thermohydraulics

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) with circulating fuel are interesting in many aspects, especially due to design possibilities they offer. This design choice has many implications for reactor safety and physics. It offers advantages, like good temperature feedbacks even for fast reactors, single-phase flow, in-line salt reprocessing etc. On the other hand, using a liquid and circulating fuel means that some dedicated codes are required for simulating the physics of the reactor. Indeed, the transport of delayed neutrons precursors depends on the velocity field and thus on turbulence, which must be taken into account. To achieve this goal (as other before with embedded neutronics inside the thermohydraulic solver [1] or with external neutronic solver [2]), a new coupled neutronics-thermohydraulics code named FluenTFM was developed. As its name suggests, it couples the well-known commercial Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) solver Ansys Fluent with the Transient Fission Matrices (TFM) approach. Fluent has been validated in many cases and benefits from extensive user experience, particularly within Orano. All the turbulence models available in the thermohydraulic solver can be used for the coupling, which makes it very flexible. Using Ansys products also provides access to Computer-Aided Design (CAD) and meshing, which are required for the applications of this paper. The TFM approach uses a Monte Carlo (MC) code to compute the spatial probability densities for neutrons to induce a fission based on their emission position. This process effectively turns a MC computation into a deterministic one, resulting in fast kinetic calculations while retaining most of the spatial effects and avoiding the complex approximations made by classical deterministic codes.

*max.begue@lpsc.in2p3.fr

This paper will start with some details about FluenTFM. First, the TFM approach will be detailed in the section 2.1. Then, Ansys Fluent and the implementation of FluenTFM as user defined functions inside Fluent will be detailed in the sections 2.2 to 2.4. In the section 3 of this paper, an example of application will be shown on a MSFR-like reactor [3] (described in section 3.1). A comparison between TFM-OpenFOAM [4] [5] and FluenTFM will be presented on a steady-state simulation in section 3.3 and on a reactivity insertion transient in the section 3.4.

2. COUPLING DESCRIPTION

2.1. The TFM Approach

The TFM approach provides a method for performing fast computations in coupled simulations [5]. It uses a Monte Carlo (MC) code on a meshed geometry to compute reaction probabilities from one cell to another. This is made by sampling neutron histories, recording birth and absorption location, whether they induce a fission and the associated times. This process is done for prompt and delayed neutrons independently because of their different energy emission, leading to different interaction probabilities. In the end, 7 matrices are computed: 4 for neutron production by fission (prompt to prompt: $\bar{\bar{K}}_{p \rightarrow p}$; prompt to delayed $\bar{\bar{K}}_{p \rightarrow d}$; delayed to prompt $\bar{\bar{K}}_{d \rightarrow p}$; delayed to delayed $\bar{\bar{K}}_{d \rightarrow d}$), 2 for the absorption (prompt and delayed) and one for the transport time of prompt neutrons. For example, the element $\left(\bar{\bar{K}}_{p \rightarrow p}\right)_{i,j}$ indicates the quantity of prompt neutrons produced in cell i by a prompt neutron created in cell j at the previous generation. The TFM operators will not be fully detailed in this paper but a complete description of the TFM approach can be found in [5].

The fission matrices can be used to compute effective kinetic parameters (generation time l_{eff} and delayed neutron fraction β_{eff}) and the neutron population evolution (equation 1 and 2)

$$\frac{d\bar{N}_p}{dt} = \frac{1}{l_{\text{eff}}} \left(\bar{\bar{K}}_{p \rightarrow p} - \bar{1} \right) \bar{N}_p + \bar{\bar{K}}_{d \rightarrow p} \sum_f \lambda_f \bar{P}_f \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d\bar{P}_f}{dt} = \frac{\beta_f}{\beta_{\text{tot}}} \left(\frac{1}{l_{\text{eff}}} \bar{\bar{K}}_{p \rightarrow d} \bar{N}_p + \bar{\bar{K}}_{d \rightarrow d} \sum_f \lambda_f \bar{P}_f \right) - \lambda_f \bar{P}_f \quad (2)$$

Where \bar{N}_p is the distribution of neutrons in the core and \bar{P}_f is the distribution of the delayed neutron precursor from the family f . Since in MSRs the fuel is moving, \bar{P}_f is also dependent on the velocity field which transports the precursors. The coupling with a thermohydraulic solver is hence required to have accurate results. For steady-state simulation, an acceleration method based on [6] is used. Instead of solving the time dependent quantities described in the equations 1 and 2, it uses the complete fission chain produced by a distribution precursors as the source term. This yields the steady state power and precursors production based on a certain precursors decay distribution.

2.2. Ansys Fluent

Ansys Fluent [7], is a commercial computational fluid dynamics solver. It also has a meshing component that was used for creating the thermohydraulic mesh of this article. Inside Ansys Fluent, the Navier-Stokes equations are solved. Those balanced equations are presented below in their incompressible form. The equation 3 is the conservation of the mass, the equation 4 is the conservation of the momentum and the equation 5 is the transport of a scalar quantity by the flow.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \bar{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \bar{u}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho \bar{u}}{\partial t} + \bar{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \bar{u} \otimes \bar{u}) = -\bar{\nabla} (p) + \nu \Delta (\bar{u}) + \bar{F} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho \square}{\partial t} + \bar{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \bar{u} \square) = \Gamma_{\square} \Delta (\square) + S_{\square} \quad (5)$$

The equations 3 and 4 are also completed by a set of equations modeling turbulence [8], depending on the chosen model. Fluent offers access to all the typical turbulence models: the classical one or two equations Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes (RANS), the intermediate Large (and Detached) Eddy Simulation (LES and DES) and the Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS). Even if all those models are available for FluenTFM, in this work, only the $k - \omega$ SST unsteady RANS model is used [9]. The choice of the model is not of first concern for this study, which focuses more on the coupling than on the absolute values of the solution.

2.3. Computations Prior to the Coupling

Before running a coupled simulation, several steps have to be completed. The first step is to create a geometry for the problem with a CAD software (for this study, Ansys Design Modeler was used). Then, two meshes are created: one for the thermohydraulic side and one for the neutronics. In practice, the cells from the neutronic mesh are then regrouped to reduce the size of the fission matrices (regrouped mesh in figure 2). This step is done inside Maya, a Python library developed at CNRS which contains wrappers for OpenFOAM, TFM and OpenMC among other things like nuclear data uncertainty evaluation. The next step is to set up an OpenFOAM case (required by Maya for this specific application) to compute the fission matrices on the grouped mesh. The matrices are computed with a dedicated version of OpenMC, a Monte Carlo code. During the calculation of the fission matrices, a dedicated OpenFOAM solver is also used to write in a file the mesh-transition matrices, enabling mapping of data between meshes (shown in figure 2). Once those requirements are fulfilled, it is possible to start a coupled simulation.

2.4. Coupling Implementation in Ansys Fluent

For the coupling, Ansys Fluent provides the ability to add User Defined Functions (UDFs), which can modify most of the behaviors of the solver. They are used at different stages of the coupling. During the initialization, the mesh-transition matrices are loaded and both the delayed neutron fractions β_f and decay constants λ_f are transmitted from Maya to Fluent for each family of precursors and for each region. This feature is useful to simulate MSRs with a separate fertile blanket for example.

After initializing all the fields, the first coupling iteration is performed. The temperature and precursor decay fields are sent to Maya through named pipes, which uses these fields to compute the power distribution and the delayed neutron precursor production. During the initialization, Maya also applies a renormalization to the fission matrices to start from a critical reactor (critical equivalent reactor assumption). The power distribution and precursor production are then converted into source terms for the energy equation and for the delayed neutron precursors transport equations. For each precursor family, one instance of equation 5 is solved for the quantity of precursor \bar{P}_f with the source term for the cell i presented in the equation 6. The second member of the source term (in blue) is actually computed inside Maya and the result is sent to Fluent.

$$S_{\bar{P}_f, i} = \rho \left[-\lambda_f \bar{P}_{f, i} + \frac{\beta_f}{\beta_{\text{tot}}} \left(\frac{1}{l_{\text{eff}}} \bar{K}_{p \rightarrow d} \bar{N}_p + \bar{K}_{d \rightarrow d} \sum_f \lambda_f \bar{P}_f \right) \right]_i \quad (6)$$

After updating the source terms, Fluent performs an outer iteration, solving all the thermohydraulic equations. This process is repeated until the solution is converged or until the maximum number of iterations defined by the user is reached. If the simulation is time-dependent, Fluent will also request the maximum time step required by the neutronics at the end of each time-step. If its value is lower than the thermohydraulic requirements, the time-step is lowered accordingly. Finally, the simulation state is recorded and the next time step starts, repeating the coupling procedure. This process is illustrated in the figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of the FluentTFM coupling iterations and initialization.

3. REACTOR SIMULATIONS

3.1. Case Setup

In this study, the coupling is presented on a MSFR-like reactor of 6 m^3 defined in [3]. The reactor power is set to $300 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$, with an average temperature maintained at 930 K . The total flow rate at the heat exchanger inlet is set to 4100 kg/s , resulting in an average velocity of 1 m/s in the heat exchanger region. The physical quantities used are listed in table I. They correspond to a NaCl - UCl_3 - PuCl_3 , but are not up to date. Once again, the result in itself does not have to be extremely precise, as long as the parameters between the two codes are identical. All model constants, including the turbulent Prandtl number, are set to their default values.

Physical quantity	Value
Density ρ	$3450 - 0.77T$ [kg /m ³]
Dynamic viscosity μ	$8.8 \times 10^{-5} e^{(3500/T)}$ [kg /m /s]
Heat capacity C_p	$660 - 0.034T$ [J/kg/K]
Thermal conductivity k_{th}	$0.72 - 2.1 \times 10^{-4}T$ [W /m /K]

Table I. Thermophysical quantities used for the reactivity insertion transient.

3.2. Meshes

As mentioned in the section 2.3, three meshes are used:

- One for thermohydraulics, refined in the near-wall region, with a large number of cells.
- One for the OpenMC calculation, refined inside the core, with fewer cells than the thermohydraulic one. Indeed, OpenMC stops the neutrons at each cell interface, leading to very long computation times for meshes with a large number of cells.
- One for the matrices, based on the neutronic mesh but with regrouped cells to reduce the size of the matrices.

The last one is based on the neutronic mesh, but smaller cells or low-importance cells (e.g. in the recirculation pipes or the heat exchanger) are grouped to reduce the size of the matrices.

In this study, the thermohydraulic mesh has about 2 millions cells and was done with Fluent meshing. The basic neutronic mesh was made with Ansys Meshing and counts 150 000 cells (30 000 in the core and 90 000 in the reflector). The mesher is different in each case because the physics to be solved are different. With the thermohydraulics, boundary layers have to be solved correctly and the orthogonality of the mesh is a huge concern. For neutronic, the goal is to have a good mesh inside the core while reducing as much as possible the total number of cells. Finally, a third mesh is created directly with Maya. According to the distance to the center of the core, the cells from the neutronic mesh are grouped to reduce the size of the matrices. The number of cells after grouping depends on the model used for neutronics. The most complex model, TFM with correlated sampling (TFM-CS), can use up to 300 cells. In the future, this constraint will be relaxed by implementing the model with sparse matrices. Indeed, it is a transport computation and the complexity of the temperature interpolation is scaling as N_{cells}^3 [10]. The model TFM-ij, scaling as N_{cells}^2 , can use up to 10 000 cells, is still a transport computation. It is not as precise as the TFM-CS model on the local thermal feedbacks, but the increase in cell number also increases the spatial resolution. The last model available is the point kinetic with correlated sampling, which can handle more than 100 000 cells. It is precise for the thermal feedbacks, but it is not a transport computation and the precursor distribution have no impact on the shape of the neutron flux (only the amplitude). In this study, the TFM-CS was used with 150 cells. The three meshes are presented in the figure 2.

Even if OpenFOAM isn't used during transient simulations, it is used to create the mesh-transition matrices between the thermohydraulic and neutronic meshes. This choice was made because the mapping is very difficult to do with Fluent UDFs and easy with OpenFOAM. During the simulations, FluentTFM uses those maps to convert data from one mesh to another.

3.3. Reactor Steady-State Computation

Before being able to compute any transient, the steady-state fields of the reactor have to be computed. At this stage, the power produced by the core is fixed to the nominal value and the average temperature of the fuel is also imposed at each time-step (or each iteration for Fluent steady-state simulations). The temperature of the intermediate circuit is then computed to extract the nominal power of the core and the total quantity of precursors is also fixed to its equilibrium value by normalizing the value of $\bar{P}_{f,i}$.

Figure 2. All level of meshes used for FluenTFM. In the grouped mesh, the colors indicate how neutronic cells are grouped for the matrices

This ensures that the volume integral of the sink term in equation 6 is equal to the integral of the creation term.

In order to verify the implementation of the coupling, the same situation is simulated using TFM-OpenFOAM. All the numerical methods are set to second order in OpenFOAM and Fluent, and the $k - \omega$ SST with default parameters is used in both cases. Since they share the same implementation of the TFM approach (via the Maya library), the results between FluenTFM and TFM-OpenFOAM are expected to be similar. Both temperature fields at steady state are presented in figure 3.

Figure 3. Temperature fields at the center plane of the core for FluenTFM (left) and TFM-OpenFOAM (right). The profile was averaged over 30 seconds.

In the FluenTFM simulation, the circulating effective delayed neutron fraction $\beta_{\text{eff}}^{\text{circ}}$ computed as the margin to prompt criticality $1 - k_p$, is 181 pcm. On the other hand, with TFM-OpenFOAM, $\beta_{\text{eff}}^{\text{circ}}$ is evaluated at 182 pcm, which is in very good agreement with FluenTFM.

At this point, it is important to note that even if the setups are as close as possible between FluenTFM and TFM-OpenFOAM, it is also expected that some differences between both codes will appear for the steady-state. This is caused by the fact the flow is intrinsically unstable and even the steady-state simulations (time-independent formulation) oscillate. This is why the temperature fields presented on the figure 3 are averaged over multiple seconds. This disparity is further increased by the small differences of solver parameters for the thermohydraulics. Indeed the control for the pump power and the intermediate heat exchanger are slightly different. In FluenTFM, the target is set as a mass flow-rate while in TFM-OpenFOAM, it is specified as a volumetric flow-rate. For the heat exchanger, A source term in the momentum equation is used to represent the pressure losses in TFM-Fluent while a full porous media model is used in TFM-OpenFOAM. This leads to slightly different flow distributions and

an offset in the core temperature.

3.4. Reactivity Insertion

In order to verify FluenTFM versus TFM-OpenFOAM coupling, 1000 pcm of reactivity are inserted in the core in 0.1 seconds. The transients are performed using the TFM with correlated sampling (TFM-CS) kinetic model. This transient was chosen because on small time scales, it is mostly the coupling that is tested, while results on longer times depend strongly on the flow distribution and on the initial velocity field.

In figure 4, the total fission power is plotted over time. Both codes show really good agreement with discrepancies appearing on the later part of the transient, as expected. At the beginning of the transient, the peak power is higher with FluenTFM, reaching 630% of the nominal power while the fission power reaches 620% of the nominal power in the TFM-OpenFOAM simulation. On the opposite, the power in the plateau is higher for TFM-OpenFOAM with 610% of the nominal value and 603% for FluenTFM. The computation time of the two codes is comparable, but TFM-OpenFOAM is faster. Indeed, even if performing an outer iteration in Fluent is faster than in OpenFOAM, the number of outer iterations required at each time step in FluenTFM is larger.

Figure 4. Fission power during an insertion of 1000 pcm in 0.1 seconds.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A new tool for neutronic-thermohydraulic coupled simulations was developed for MSRs. FluenTFM uses Ansys Fluent, the well known thermohydraulic simulation code for solving the Navier-Stokes equations and the TFM approach encapsulated in the library Maya for neutronics. Fluent was chosen for the quality control, the multiple turbulence models and the experience detained by Orano Projects on the software. On the other hand, the TFM approach was used for its ability to speed up the time dependent kinetic simulations while still solving the neutron transport.

Steady state and reactivity insertion transients were computed with FluenTFM and the results were compared with TFM-OpenFOAM, another coupled simulation code developed since 2013 and used at CNRS. The two codes show good agreement, giving confidence that the implementations are correct and that further studies can be carried out. Power stability in MSR is an important concern and DES simulations will be performed using FluenTFM. The impact of radiative heat transfer will also be addressed in future studies. Finally, the coupling will be used to compute neutron noise signals for MSRs, allowing to study the impact of the circulating fuel on the noise.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Corentin Macqueron, Johann William and Gregory Caplin from Orano Projects for their sustained help and advices during the whole development of the code.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Fiorina, I. Clifford, M. Aufiero, and K. Mikityuk. "GeN-Foam: a novel OpenFOAM® based multi-physics solver for 2D/3D transient analysis of nuclear reactors." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 294**, pp. 24–37 (2015).
- [2] F. Martin. *Advanced neutronics-thermohydraulics studies for MSRs (Molten Salt Reactors)*. Ph.D. thesis, Université Grenoble Alpes [2020-....] (2024).
- [3] T. Sornay. *Démarche et outils de calcul pour l'étude multiphysique et multicritère des réacteurs à sels fondus de type SMR*. Ph.D. thesis, Université Grenoble Alpes (ComUE) (2024).
- [4] A. Laureau, M. Aufiero, P. Rubiolo, E. Merle-Lucotte, and D. Heuer. "Transient Fission Matrix: Kinetic calculation and kinetic parameters β eff and Λ eff calculation." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 85**, pp. 1035–1044 (2015-11).
- [5] A. Laureau, D. Heuer, E. Merle-Lucotte, P. Rubiolo, M. Allibert, and M. Aufiero. "Transient coupled calculations of the Molten Salt Fast Reactor using the Transient Fission Matrix approach." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 316**, pp. 112–124 (2017). URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S002954931730081X>.
- [6] F. Perdu. *Contributions aux études de sûreté pour des filières innovantes de réacteurs nucléaires*. Ph.D. thesis, Université Joseph-Fourier-Grenoble I (2003).
- [7] Ansys Inc, Southpointe 2600 Ansys Drive Canonsburg, PA 15317. *Ansys Fluent User's Guide*, 2023 r1 edition (2023).
- [8] Ansys Inc, Southpointe 2600 Ansys Drive Canonsburg, PA 15317. *Ansys Fluent Theory Guide*, 2023 r1 edition (2023).
- [9] F. R. Menter. "Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications." *AIAA journal*, **volume 32**(8), pp. 1598–1605 (1994).
- [10] A. Laureau, L. Buiron, and B. Fontaine. "Local correlated sampling Monte Carlo calculations in the TFM neutronics approach for spatial and point kinetics applications." *EPJ N-Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, **volume 3**, p. 16 (2017).